

SETTING OF THE GELS OF SODIUM OLEATE AND STEARATE IN SOME ORGANIC SOLVENTS. PART I. TIME AND TEMPERATURE OF SETTING

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The study of the time and temperature of setting of gels of sodium oleate in nujol, pinene and xylene and of sodium stearate in nujol and benzyl alcohol has shown that (1) the time of setting for any concentration depends upon the rate of cooling; (2) the setting temperature of a given system is constant and independent of the rate of cooling, but increases with increase in concentration of the soap in the system.

Most of the organic gels are formed either by cooling or by heating the gel-forming systems. Hence, the time of setting of organic gels should necessarily be determined by factors which influence the rate of cooling of the gel-forming solutions. This fact was realised by Trotman and Ball and others (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1934, 53, 225T; *Curr. Sci.*, 1940, 9, 119, 459) who took the time of setting of an organic gel to be "the time required by a solution prepared at a high temperature to set when cooled in a thermostat maintained at a constant low temperature". Their results bring out clearly that the time of setting of an organic gel increases with the increase in the temperature of the surrounding.

The previous work has laid stress on the time of setting of gels as a fundamental property of the system. The importance of the temperature of setting does not seem to have received corresponding notice. In the present investigation the effects of concentration and the rate of cooling on the time and temperature of setting have been studied systematically in the case of the gel-forming solutions of sodium oleate in nujol, xylene and pinene and of sodium stearate in nujol and benzyl alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium oleate and stearate were products of B.D.H. Nujol (d 0.8743; μ 1.4810) was obtained from Messers. Stauco Incorporated, New Jersey, U.S.A. Benzyl alcohol was superfine product of W. J. Bush and Co.. The purity of pinene and xylene was checked by determining their boiling points from time to time.

Gel-forming Solutions.—Gels of sodium oleate in nujol, pinene and xylene were prepared in the usual manner (Prasad and Hattiangdi, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, 21A, 1) in boiling tubes of internal diameter 2.8 cm.. The soap initially swelled and finally went into solution at 200°, 140° and 130° respectively. Gels of sodium stearate in nujol and benzyl alcohol were prepared similarly in boiling tubes of the same diameter. The soap initially swelled and finally went into solution at 200° and 110° respectively.

Time and Temperature of Setting.—The time of setting was determined by the Flemming's method (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1902, 41, 427). The effect of rate of cooling

on the time of setting was determined in two ways, namely, by keeping the solutions prepared at temperatures mentioned (i) at several lower temperatures and (ii) at each such temperature in tubes of internal diameters 2.2 and 3.2 cm. as well.

The temperature of setting was determined as follows: A thermometer was inserted at the centre of the tube containing the solution after all the air bubbles were removed. The tube was then transferred to a thermostat maintained at some constant low temperature. The gel-forming solution was periodically examined to determine whether it had set to a gel. The temperature indicated at the point of setting was taken to be the temperature of setting. The exact temperature of setting was determined by repeating the experiment several times.

DISCUSSION

The general nature of results is the same in all cases. They lead to the following conclusions:

(i) The time of setting for any concentration depends on the rate of cooling; it increases as the rate of cooling is reduced and *vice versa*.

(ii) Under identical conditions of cooling, the solutions of higher soap content take shorter time to set.

(iii) For a given concentration, the setting temperature is constant and is independent of the rate of cooling.

(iv) The setting temperature increases as the concentration of the soap is increased.

It was also noted independently that when a solution was kept in a thermostat maintained at a temperature even one degree higher than the setting temperature of the solution, it did not set to a rigid gel but afforded a highly viscous mass. These observations establish that the setting temperature is the highest temperature at which a gel-forming solution sets to a gel and that all the processes are involved in the setting of a gel during the cooling of the solution from T_s , the temperature at which it has been prepared, to T_g , the temperature of setting.

It appears from the above that the time of setting of these gels is the time taken by the gel-forming solutions from T_s to T_g , when cooled in a thermostat kept at a given temperature T_0 . This conclusion was verified by the study of the cooling curves of the gel-forming solutions under the same conditions as employed for the determination of the time of setting. It was found that the cooling of the solutions obeyed the Newton's law before, during and after gelation; the values of the time (T_0) required for cooling of a solution from T_s to T_g , when cooled at T_0 , calculated by applying the equation

$$\log (T_s - T_0) - \log (T_g - T_0) = Kt_0,$$

agreed fairly well with the corresponding observed values for the time of setting.